

SMART SPENDING: HARNESSING AI TO OPTIMIZE CLOUD COST MANAGEMENT

Hemanth Swamy

Independent Researcher, USA

ABSTRACT

Among SMEs, cloud computing is becoming more popular. Cloud resource optimization is becoming a top concern for many businesses because of the substantial impact that cloud resource costs have on their operations. A lot of people have thought about ways to lower the price of cloud services and optimize cloud computing resources based on actual demand. These optimization strategies often provide unsatisfactory results because real-world cloud workloads are multi-factor, dynamic, and irregular. An innovative method for configuring cloud resources in the most cost-effective way is presented in this article; it makes use of an AI learning algorithm. This comprehensive solution operates in a closed loop, learning the system's use patterns and automatically detecting and avoiding abnormal circumstances without any external supervision or setup. System load and cloud provider price plans are both able to be adjusted by our solution. Data from a real-world system was used to test it on Microsoft's cloud environment, Azure. The results of the experiments show that an 85% decrease in costs was achieved during a 10-month period.

Keywords: Cloud Resource Usage Prediction, Machine Learning, And Resource Cost Optimization

Cite this Article: Hemanth Swamy, Smart Spending: Harnessing AI to Optimize Cloud Cost Management, International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research and Development (IJAIRD), 2(2), 2024, pp. 40-55.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJAIRD/VOLUME_2_ISSUE_2/IJAIRD_02_02_003.pdf

INTRODUCTION

One of the most potent computing technologies with several benefits has arisen in the era of the Internet: cloud computing. With cloud computing, users have unlimited, remote access to any and all kinds of computer programs. From storing and retrieving data to accessing servers, software, and databases, the apps cover it all. You may access the data whenever you want, from any location. In this scenario, user ownership of the hardware is not necessary. The data centers that make up a cloud may be found all over the world [1]. Nowadays, most fault tolerance methods focus on creating clones of virtual machines to replace them in case of failure, instead than trying to forecast when a failure would occur. When a virtual machine fails, several of the existing methods prioritize migration rather recovery.

This is because there are issues with server availability and limited resources. Fairness, migration forecasting, and just anticipating failure are all instances of algorithms having a single goal [2]. Integrating AI has become a game-changer in the dynamic world of cloud computing, revolutionizing resource allocation and increasing efficiency [3]. The demand for cloud computing has skyrocketed in the last decade, setting a new standard for many other applications, including AI, big data, the Internet of Things, and many more. The ever-increasing complexity of cloud computing is a direct outcome of its popularity, which in turn increases the risk of software or hardware failure. The architecture is so intricate that problems may go undetected for an extended period of time, leading to increased maintenance costs [4]. One promising new area of the IoT that will enable smart IoT applications is artificial intelligence (AIoT). When it comes to AIoT, smart edge computing solutions significantly outperform basic cloud-aided IoT architecture in terms of processing speed and cost. Nevertheless, a well-thought-out plan to maximize AIoT energy efficiency using intelligent edge computing is still missing [5]. Rapid advancements in energy as well as environmental biotechnologies have been propelled by pressing social concerns including pollution management, energy security, and climate change in the last several decades. Major advantages in determining ideal process parameters and lowering total proccostswill may be achieved by combining traditional simulation and modeling methods with computer technology and artificial intelligence [6]. The use of communication networks has now permeated many facets of modern society. The expansion of the IT sector and the maturation of cloud computing have been propelled by innovations in network infrastructure. The use of AI and deep learning technologies makes networks smarter, which in turn leads to more widespread use of conceptsr in networked communication optimization approaches [7].

Cloud Cost Optimization: Allocating the most suitable and cost-effective cloud resources for every workload or application is the goal of cloud cost optimization. To make sure cloud expenditures are suitable for the organization's needs, it weighs the necessary performance against the necessary cost as well as compliance and security. Each workload in a cloud installation is distinct, and its needs change as time goes on. We need to determine performance standards for every task using domain expertise and real operational KPIs in order to minimize cloud expenses. Saving money without sacrificing performance is the goal of optimization. Optimizing costs in the cloud is an ongoing process that adapts to new needs in applications as well as to the ever-changing nature of cloud pricing and available services. To optimize cloud costs, you need precise data, analytics, and automated solutions since cloud systems are so complicated. Budgets, AWS cost forecasts, and optimal cloud cost optimization can all be done using the Cost Management panel. A Cost anomaly identification option is available on the console; it uses machine learning to track expenditure and use in order to spot unusual patterns. When we are about to reach or over our budgeted amounts, we may set up notifications to let you know. We can avoid unforeseen expenses and stay on track with the budget if we identify and fix the underlying causes of anomalies. One way to keep your company's cloud computing costs in check is via cloud cost optimization, a methodical strategy. There is more to optimizing your cloud expenditures than just decreasing costs. To get the most out of your cloud budget, they will instead do a thorough evaluation of your present cloud use, looking for inefficiencies and removing waste. A more transparent cloud environment allows for more efficient use of resources while maintaining a healthy balance between cost, performance, security, and availability; these are the four pillars upon which cloud cost optimization rests. From a more economical cloud environment to a faster-growing company, optimizing cloud expenses is a continuous process with many advantages.

- **Reduce your expenditure.** Without vigilant management, cloud expenses have the potential to vanish into thin air. You can save money on unnecessary expenses by making cloud cost optimization a top priority. That way, you can use that money toward other important things like manufacturing and recruiting.
- **Ensure resource efficiency.** Rightsizing resources, avoiding over-provisioning, as well as paying for unused capacity are all part of effective cloud cost optimization.
- **Gain budget control and predictability.** A predictable cloud budget is the result of optimization. We may avoid unpleasant surprises and improve our strategic planning with an accurate prediction of cloud spending made possible by efficient cost management techniques.
- **Improve oversight and transparency.** You can see exactly where your money is going when you optimize your cloud costs and then report on them. With this newfound knowledge, we may better connect technological and commercial objectives while simultaneously increasing responsibility.

The introduction of multiple computing paradigms, such as the IoT, fog, and cloud, is necessary to enhance human life quality in light of the exponential development of data generated by smart devices. In contrast to the previous two models, the new cloud computing paradigm moves cloud layer amenities to the network's periphery, bringing resource allocation processes closer to the end user and lowering processing times and traffic overhead [8]. One new way to manage massive amounts of data is via cloud computing. Massive replication placement and selection processing have been carried out on the cloud. Prior research on replication mostly relied on mathematical models, with less attention paid to AI. Swarm intelligence algorithms include the Artificial Bee Colony [9]. There is a mutual advantage between database management systems and AI. A positive aspect of AI is its potential to enhance database intelligence. In the cloud in particular, large-scale database servers, varied applications, and diversified user bases make conventional empirical database optimization techniques like cost estimates, join order choices, knob adjustment, index and view selection, etc., insufficient. Fortunately, learning-based techniques have the potential to address this problem. [10]. As data controllers collect an ever-increasing amount of personally identifiable information, the need for robust cloud security measures becomes more apparent. An important aspect of cloud security assertions is the presence of both private data that is not encrypted and publicly accessible data that has been outsourced. Because of the repercussions of data breaches, a sophisticated legal data protection limitation is necessary. The majority of current methods for handling sensitive data do not provide enough privacy, prompting researchers to look for ways to preserve privacy in the cloud [11]. An important part of running a smart industrial park with minimal carbon emissions is managing the electrical equipment in real time, including renewable energy, adjustable loads, and storage units. Modern technology has made possible the intelligent optimization of the electrical management of devices via the advent of the digital twin, which investigates the use of cloud-edge device cooperation and artificial intelligence to build accurate digital representations of physical equipment [12]. To better serve their residents and the city as a whole, smart cities use artificial intelligence techniques. Smart apps, from the perspective of the user, should move computation closer to the edges of the cloud, where it can be more easily accessed by citizens with minimal latency. From the perspective of cloud designers, however, Pareto solutions are necessary for the trade-off between energy, time, and cost [13]. Service robots are becoming more commonplace as a result of advancements in computing and AI. Meanwhile, practically all small businesses cannot afford the high production costs of robots. The structure of the service robot as well as the sharing of resources across robot groups are the two most significant technological restrictions. Every single one of the many uses for service robots involves some kind of path-planning problem.

No matter the application, you'll need to optimize paths, compute quickly, and keep computing time to a minimum [14]. An array of sectors, including healthcare, transportation, agriculture, and security, have been quick to adopt AI methods since their inception. Customer investment costs may be reduced, and data- and computation-intensive AI applications can be deployed faster with the help of edge computing environments that provide latency-assured AI as a service [15].

RELATED WORK

The researcher's goal in that study is to better understand how hospitals may enhance their financial management by using cloud and wireless networking technologies [16]. When it comes to managing their finances, healthcare organizations confront a number of obstacles, including ineffectiveness, growth planning, and budgeting. Given that situation, it's clear that their financial management needs some serious optimization. By automating mundane processes and using cloud computing powered by artificial intelligence, businesses are able to boost their output per employee. To improve hospital financial administration, that study proposes a system that makes use of cloud computing and wireless networking technologies. A combination of fuzzy neural systems is used to make the model operate. After comparing the suggested model to preexisting fuzzy logic as well as neural network models, they find that it achieves a 97.56% accuracy rate while using very little resources, making it ideal for use in hospital financial management. Finding the best way to get from a poorly performing system to a well-performing one is the goal of the writers in [17]. Timely failure prediction of virtual machines is critical to avoid problems like wasted resources, energy, and money. Problems with the reliability of virtual machines, or VMs, have plagued cloud computing since its inception. To ensure the continuation of service, preventive measures are an essential part of the fault tolerance system. Because of that, improving and highlighting virtual machines' proactive failure prediction is crucial. Reduced downtime and improved scalability are the primary drivers behind this. One virtual machine (VM) had its resources that were supposed to fail transferred to another VM in a secure manner. This study's descriptive research [18] delves into the process of creating and deploying an AI-powered system that optimizes cloud resources on the fly according to application workloads. That article explores the fundamentals of AI in cloud resource administration, looks at the problems with conventional optimization methods, and then shows how AI may be used to optimize cloud resources in the actual world. To provide a thorough resource for researchers as well as professionals in the subject, they have included keywords, pertinent papers, and references. In order to enhance the fault tolerance, a simulation-driven framework has been developed in the study [19]. In order to optimize costs and achieve reliability in workflow models, they invented RACO (RedundancyfewAware Cost Optimization). The RACO mechanism is divided into submechanisms, one of which is fault tolerance optimization; the others solve reliability issues and optimize costs by adding parameters. When they take into account the many scientific procedures that take the cost parameter into account, authors find that their model performs better than the previous model when evaluating RACO. The researchers in [20] suggested a framework for ubiquitous clouds and used an AI optimization method to the optimization technique of a network for point-to-point signal transmission. In that work, researchers test and examine the suggested approach for various use cases. The suggested approach enhances optimization efficiency and decreases optimization cost considerably, according to experimental findings, by fully using the benefits of communication network substances as compared to state-of-the-art techniques. Using - Optimization and the knapsack problem, the authors of [21] evaluate the cost distance and provide many cloud-based shortest-route alternatives for replication and its distribution across data centers.

Utilizing ABC to solve the authors route combined with lower applied cost problems the knapsack approach, we can find the best place to replicate based on distance or the fastest routes with the lowest prices. In order to maximize efficiency while minimizing expenses in the system that has been described, multi-objective optimization using the artificial bee colony (MOABC) method may be used. By considering the lowest distance and quantity of data transfers, MOABC may determine the ideal location for data copies, allowing for low-cost data replication using the knapsack technique. For the purpose of robot route planning, the authors of the aforementioned article [22] want to suggest the Google Cloud Platform and the Amazon Web Service platforms. Finding out what happens when service robots use a cloud computing framework is the main goal. The cloud computing method moves the computational burden away from robots and onto a remote server. multi-objective deciding the path-planning algorithm to use for robot navigation on the Google Cloud Platform, three options were evaluated; while utilizing AWS, three kinds of environments—dense, moderate, and sparse—were considered. That research compares and contrasts the outcomes of utilizing cloud services for robot route planning with those of using the conventional technique. Using a cloud platform, as suggested, works better here. In the study, the time element is given and identified in a key way. That the respective relative latency reduces with increasing environment size is the main benefit of that experiment. So, it seems like there could be some benefits to expanding the scope of work using cloud platforms. A versatile method of operation is provided by the authors in optimization with the ability to configure the shortest quality rate with model complexity proportions for the AI tasks together. They also proposed edge. -AIaaS-specific architecture for model deployment. The management may increase the energy and delay the effectiveness AI services while still achieving the desired result quality by using generally utilized resource allocation methodologies. To solve the configuration subproblem of the job, they formulate an energy-delay minimization issue based on CMDA and propose a relaxing method based on polynomial regression. They simulate and evaluate ImageNet classification as well as COCO object recognition tasks using state-of-the-art deep learning models. Qua The quality outcomes regression models and accompanying result quality charts demonstrate the proposed approach. Researchers provide a method in [24] that makes algorithmic supervised learning at the edge simpler. It breaks down complicated models into a series of smaller classifiers, creating a hierarchy of discriminative models. By comparing the results of three distinct iterations of that approach, they may determine if that suggestion is applicable to a HAR setting. In addition, its processing time-based computational cost is examined in various Edge devices with limited resources. That strategy has the potential to surpass existing ensemble approaches, such as the Stastackingchnique, according to the experimental data. In addition, it drastically cuts the computing cost of classification jobs by over 60% while maintaining a respectable level of accuracy (around 3.5%). That demonstrates how that approach has the ability to encourage more effective and environmentally friendly categorization solutions while simultaneously decreasing the need for resources and energy in IoT infrastructures. To identify chirality in perovskites, the authors of [25] built a smart cloud lab that combines lab automation, cloud servers, and AI. Thanks to the MAOSIC platform, which stands for materials acceleration systems in the cloud, that virtual lab now allows distant users to create experiments on demand. It is possible to do synthesis, Whicharacterizationr optimization autonomously using AIoT technology. In the beginning, researchers worked remotely to create optically responsive inorganic perovskite nanocrystals (IPNCs) via inversion control and temperature-dependent circular dichroism. The MAOSIC-discovered dual-pattern-induced processes, which include both structural designs and screw dislocations, were the subject of a comprehensive examination. Offline theoretical study revealed studies materials' internal thermodynamic processes. In the cloud computing paradigm, the optimization technique known as artificial bee chicken swarm optimisation ioptimizationild a virtual machine replacement strategy in the

study [ation of artificial bee colonies and chicken swarm [23], is known optimizationO algorithm. That approach used the service provider to position virtual machines according to their needs in order to finish certain tasks. In order to optimize the cloud system's performance in areas such as load, CPU utilization, memory, and power, the recommended ABCSO-based VM placement strategy is used throughout the initial design phase. The fitness function takes into account variables the data migration cosuch asload, and power consumption to identify the optimal virtual machine migration approach. In order to reduce the carbon dioxide footprints per barrel produced, improved cloud-based fluid dispersion imaging was suggested in [27]. That would enable better and more optimal production. It is essential to know where the stored fluids are in order to store CO₂. Because of the significant link between electromagnetics and fluid resistivity, electromagnetic imaging of reservoir fluids is chosen. The data acquisition and interpretation processes are too time-consuming to have a meaningful impact on field operations' cost efficiency. Authors may reduce operational outputs to near real-time and close to 24 hours for analysis using cloud-based data collection and artificial intelligence. What this means is that this technology, which has the potential to be utilized for exploration, production, and monitoring, may progress much farther. Because of that, the application envelope may be expanded to include much noisier situations, allowing for the optimization of real-time collection depending on the data obtained. Optimal solution provision is the goal of the approach used in [28]. There is a great deal of activity in all these areas of study. In the realm of cloud computing, there is a quick vision, models, and obstacles to overcome in order to optimize resources efficiently. Considering the quality of services along with their characteristics, the essential job is to allocate these effective assets and create algorithms for optimizing their time and cost. The algorithms' high computing cost and poor accuracy both have a negative impact on the efficiency of these methods. Hence, the idea of fuzzy systems—which incorporate fuzzy reasoning and logical thinking, fuzzy controllers, fuzzy sets, rough sets, etc.—is crucial to the development of these techniques. According to the situation, the study is based on rough set theory and the technology acceptance model. For circumstances requiring qualitative analysis, RST is an excellent approach that may provide significant results. Inductive reasoning, data reduction, pattern recognition, automated categorization, learning algorithms, and the discovery of new information are all aspects of that method. Model slices utilizing network function virtualization are proposed in the study as a solution to multipath transmission [29]. To determine which unit makes decisions about the routing and storage of the model slices, an optimization issue is first created. The topic is stated as a mixed-integer linear programming issue with the goal of minimizing transmission costs within the constraints imposed by the available network resources. Creating a heuristic approach based on the Steiner tree issue is the second stage in resolving the optimization challenge. Ultimately, they are able to use the transfer learning method to simulate three slices from VGG16: one general slice and two particular slices. When dealing with large networks and many destination nodes, the results show that the transmission strategy for model slices maximizes bandwidth usage efficiency. In [30], the writers provide a thorough introduction to the subject of AI optimization of edge offerings in IoV. A foundational understanding of the IoV, EC, and AI is laid out first, along with certain related notions. Second, they investigate the application of AI to the problems of service offloading and edge server placement by reviewing the IoV edge service frameworks. To wrap things up, they go over some of the unanswered questions about AI optimization of edge services.

PROPOSED WORK

A. Research Issues: Systems hosted in the cloud can include a wide variety of resources and may be very complex. The resources' demand fluctuates over time due to factors such as: 1) user-generated usage patterns that are time- and day-dependent; 2) end-point machine configuration usage patterns (i.e., IoT usage); 3) modifications to system configuration (i.e., new features, devices); 4) temporary conditions that cause accidental changes (e.g., software bugs, communication problems). System availability is critical. When the demand for cloud assets changes, the configuration of those resources needs to be adjusted, which implies they need to be scaled. More or less resources may be made available. One way to scale up a virtual machine is to increase its CPU settings, while another way is to supply another instance of the same VM. Efficiently delivering the same amount of computing power may be achieved by scaling up or scaling out, depending on the price plan of the cloud provider. Since scaling takes time, it's best to do it ahead of time, which necessitates predicting how much resources will be used.

Fig.1. System Model

B. Scheduling and Cost Monitoring using DRL

Effective monitoring of cloud charges may be achieved using an AI-based solution. The three-pronged approach to cloud monitoring that Anodot employs consists of:

- **Cost monitoring:** One major benefit of AI-based monitoring over general cloud cost reporting is that it provides service, region, team, and instance-specific charges. A lot less effort is wasted when problems do arise because of this fine-grained approach.
- **Usage monitoring:** One major benefit of AI-based monitoring over general cloud cost reporting is that it provides service, region, team, and instance-specific charges. A lot less effort is wasted when problems do arise because of this fine-grained approach.
- **Cost forecasting:** At last, the AI-powered system can absorb all cloud-based metrics, even in multi-cloud setups, figure out how it normally operates, and provide cost estimates, paving the way for better allocation of resources and budgeting.

One subfield of AI, known as "deep reinforcement learning," uses data and algorithms to learn from past mistakes and successes, which allows it to make predictions and suggestions. By identifying and eliminating inefficiencies and waste, as well as discovering new ways to save money, it becomes a powerful tool for cost management. Deep reinforcement learning has many applications in the realm of cloud expenditure management, some of which include:

Predictive cost analysis

- Strengthening from Within Learning may be used to forecast cloud expenditures by analyzing use and demand trends. This helps with budgeting and allocating resources wisely.

Resource optimization

- Strengthening from within When it comes to managing cloud resource allocation, learning really shines at spotting underused resources, making suggestions to increase resource usage, and suggesting instance kinds that are both cost-effective and efficient.

Automated spending oversight

- Strengthening from within the cloud: expenditure is kept in control by learning to efficiently identify occasions when spending exceeds projected levels and provide methods for cost reduction.

C. Cost Modeling

We make the assumption that the system is time-slotted, with each time slot lasting for $t \in [1 \dots T]$. Hot and cool tiers, represented by subscripts h as well as c in the symbols used, are comprised of a collection of data storage services in this paradigm.

There are two components to the price of any storage service. (i) s_h and s_c indicate the storage cost in hot and cold temperatures in terms of bytes per unit size and days per unit time, respectively. (ii) a_h and a_c specify the cost of entry in the warm and cold categories, respectively. a_h is a function of t_h^r and t_h^w and which stand for the expense of a large number of reads and writes, respectively. Thus, $a_h = t_h^r + t_h^w$. Please be informed that in all tiers, the cost of bandwidth for data writing is free. Similarly, a_c May be expressed as the total of t_c^r and t_c^w . Also included is the cost of data retrieval per unit size, which is represented by b_c . Hence, $a_c = t_c^r + t_c^w + b_c$.

Fig.2. DRL based Tasks and VMs

In time slot t , let's pretend that a user or a software program produces a collection of objects. There are three characteristics that define an object: its size, the number of reads and writes at a certain time slot ($r(t)$), and the number of reads and writes ($w(t)$). $x_{\text{tier}}(t)$ integer that, when set to 1 to indicate that an item is present in tier tier , $\in \{h, c\}$, where 0 is the default. We find the worth of in order to minimize the expenses of the storage service at every time interval t , which necessitated the subsequent definition of expenses.

Here are the premises upon which the model we put up rests. To begin, the infrastructure supporting cloud computing is a multiserver setup consisting of a fixed number of identical computers. We also don't take into account the cloud platform's vulnerability to things like network latency, server outage, and server-to-server fluctuation. Thirdly, in a cloud computing platform, all virtual machines are treated as being identical, meaning they all have identical service capacity, which is determined by the number of instructions that need to be performed. The following discussion also pertains to jobs that are self-contained and may be executed separately with the help of integrated scheduling of cloud service management nodes. Typical of cloud computing systems are VMs and jobs that are identical to one another.

As an example, a microservice design separates services into smaller, more functionally independent units with modest levels of granularity. The availability of services may be guaranteed by deploying it on several identical virtual machines. The map-reduce process on the cloud server also involves a significant number of isomorphic calculations, which may be executed using homogeneous virtual machines.

We zero in on the resource cost of the virtual machines (VMs) as a means of measuring cloud computing costs. There are two possible states for a virtual machine: open (the VM is active) and closed (the VM is not active). Further subcategorization of the open state into the resource-intensive "busy" and "idle" states is also possible. When there are fewer unused virtual machines and more actively used ones, the cloud computing platform's resource utilization goes up.

Our goal in this work is to reduce expenses and improve performance by predicting and optimizing the cloud platform's performance and cost. To do this, we have divided the VM state into different parts and developed an effective strategy.

Due to potential differences in the tasks given by service operations, various kinds of cloud VMs have varying reaction times when it comes to scheduling jobs. Keeping in line with the workload, two categories of cloud resources are: I/O-intensive VM_{i1} , to which the infrastructure layer links data-intensive devices like monitors and compute-intensive VM_{i2} , which establish connections to devices at the framework layer that perform computationally expensive tasks, including modules for encrypting and decrypting data. Every resource in the cloud is described as:

$$V_f = \{V_f^{ID}, V_f^t, V_{com}^p, V_{ity}^p, \cos t_j^{VM_e}, \cos t_j^{VM_s}\} \quad (1)$$

where V_f^{ID} is the Cloud resource ID, V_f^t is the Cloud resource type, V_{com}^p is the pace at which the cloud resource can process data, and V_{ity}^p is the cloud resource's IO speed. In addition, $\cos t_j^{VM_e}$ represents the cost per hour for utilizing or renting resources in the cloud, which varies for various kinds of resources in the security middle platform. $\cos t_j^{VM_s}$ is the virtual machine's (VM) zero-sum initial investment.

When a work is allocated to a specific cloud VM instance after the scheduling choices, it goes into a wait queue. L_f^f . Without limiting ourselves, let's say that every virtual machine instance can only run a single task in its queue at any time. The job scheduler is the central component that, according to the needs of the security company, distributes tasks to an appropriate pool of cloud resources. If there is no one else waiting to do the given work, it will go straight to the virtual machine; otherwise, it will go into a wait state first. On the basis of the assumptions made before, the response period of a task may be represented as the sum of the two components, the wait time and the execution time:

$$J_i^{rt} = J_i^{et} + J_i^{wt} \quad (2)$$

where J_i^{nt} is the job response time, J_i^{et} is when the work will be done, and J_i^{wt} it takes to get a job. When various kinds of cloud resources are scheduled, the amount of time it takes for jobs to execute varies. Due to the fact that all cloud resources run in parallel, the task transfer time for a certain kind of foreground work is almost nonexistent. Additionally, the length of the work type is the primary element influencing the execution duration of the task on the intermediate platform resource; other job types' lengths are truncated, irrelevant, and practically meaningless. Hence, the time it takes for a task to execute is:

$$J_i^{et} = \max\left(\frac{J_{cam_i}^l}{V_{cw_{mj}}^p}, \frac{J_{iy_i}^l}{V_{toy}^p}\right) \quad (3)$$

where J_t^{et} is the job execution time, $J_{com_i}^l$ is how long the job's computations must be, and J_{10}^l is the required IO length. $V_{com_j}^p$ computes at the speed of the cloud resource, as well as the rate at which the cloud resource processes IO. The main aspect that determines the duration is the kind of task. But, following the Cannikin Law principle, a work may be assigned to either the same or a different kind of cloud resource. Short task execution time is a result of the high performance of the matching kind of cloud resource, provided that the job type is compatible with the resource type. If the two are mismatched, the associated kind of cloud resource will have poor performance, resulting in significantly longer task execution times. Also, resource scheduling is impacted by the work wait time, which is described as follows:

$$J_i^{wt} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } L_j^t = 0 \\ \sum_{n=0}^t J_n^{et}, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where J_i^{wt} it takes to get a job. Jobs are promptly performed if the wait pool is empty. If not, it will have to wait. All the tasks that have come before this one have their execution times added together to form the wait time. J_1^{et} serves as the duration for which the task is carried out. In cases where the primary task J_f is set up for resource V_f and finishes processing, the following is the modified free time of the cloud resource:

$$V_j^{nt} = J_i^{wt} + J_i^{at} + J_i^{et} \quad (5)$$

Cloud resources make it possible for DRL to function as a service and provide suitable safety precautions for security services during the execution of background jobs. For scheduling and cloud computing to work, there has to be a happy medium between price, load balancing, and quality of service. Upon submitting foreground work requests, end users may define QoS requirements based on security protection levels via the DRL. Particularly in real-time settings, safety measures often have stringent reaction time requirements. By "maximum acceptable time to respond for a foreground job," we mean the quality of service standards for security services. To find out how well each foreground work was scheduled, we may use this formula to define the quality of service satisfaction:

$$Sat_{ty} = \begin{cases} 1, & J_i^{rt} \leq J_i^q \\ 0, & J_i^{rt} > J_i^q \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The execution deadline (expectation) for each foreground task and each request for service of the security services varies based on the security protection level. Pretend the cloud resource's execution result may be returned before the deadline. This signifies that the scheduling process was fruitful, the quality of service criteria were satisfied, and the capacity for security protection was activated. In any other case, this scheduling execution will fail, and the task request will be canceled. Contacting the front desk and re-executing the backup job after amending the QOS criteria is essential for the security services to function effectively in the event of a scheduling failure. Here are the definitions of foreground job costs:

$$J_i^{cost} = J_i^{et} \times \cos t_j^{VMe} + \cos t_j^{VMS} \quad (7)$$

where J_i^{cost} is the amount needed to complete the task, and J_i^{et} is the time it takes for the task to run on the cloud resource. $\cos t_j^{VMe}$ is the expense associated with using the specific cloud resource that the task is directed to, and $\cos t_j^{VMS}$ is how much the desired cloud resource will cost to launch. Because they are stored in the cloud, resources in the cloud are only used when needed, released instantly after use, and startup times are minimal. According to the wait queue architecture, data transmission and task execution occur in parallel, with run time being much greater than transfer time. Real job operation costs just have to account for run-time costs.

The agent needs minimal input from prior expertise when using deep Q-learning (DQN), an RL approach that does not need models. A value function, an agent, an environment, an action, a state, and a reward make up the RL model. $Q: \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, It seeks to foretell the course of action that optimizes the award. The return function takes its cues from the reward function. Through interactions based on trial and error, the agent determines its behaviors, and the environment progresses to the next state after each execution, $\mathcal{S}_{t+1}$. Concurrently, the agent is compensated. There is no break in the experimental replay mechanism.

$$\mathbb{R} \text{ return} = \sum_{t=1}^n \mathbb{R}_t \gamma^t \quad (8)$$

Ereturn is a weighted total of all $\mathbb{R}_t$ from beginning to end, and γ is the discount component that guides the model's attention to present or potential future rewards by weighting future benefits. One of the most popular training losses is the mean squared error (MSE) loss, which is:

$$\min_{\phi} \sum_{t=1}^{|B|} \left(r_{t_f} + \gamma \max_{\hat{a} \in \lambda} Q_{\phi}^{\text{target}}(s_{t+1}, \hat{a}) - Q_{\phi}(s_{t_t}, a_{t_t}) \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

Where B is the training minibatch and ϕ^{target} has a constant value between zero and one when the MSE loss is computed, r_t is the reward that is earned by acting on state s_t , whereas γ is the discount factor. The agent decides on certain states and provides input to the environment based on the rewards offered by the deep neural network (DNN). Absolutely every state-action pair is connected.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

We have built an optimization system that takes advantage of Azure cloud computing based on the idea from the previous section. Cloud simulator tests validated our system's efficacy; as said, a simulator shortens testing times and increases testing flexibility. You may get and modify a component's parameters, as well as see its use history, using an API that is exposed by Azure, Microsoft's cloud service. You may also get the current price plan with the Azure API. For the sake of simplicity, we will restrict our attention to the Azure cloud, namely its virtual machines (IaaS), application services (PaaS), and database management system (SaaS). The scalability of both virtual machines and app services may be done using Azure computing units (ACUs), which stand for the performance power of unified computing (CPUs). An app service's available RAM and a virtual machine's maximum input and output tasks per second are both scalable. You may scale SQL databases in proportion to storage space using Database Transaction Units (DTUs), which are a mix of utilized memory, CPU power, and IOPS level. Regardless, our solution works with any scalable cloud provider and cloud resources. Our primary prediction engine, Microsoft's Azure Machine Learning Studio, was chosen to make use of the Azure environment. You may get pre-built ML and data processing components in Machine Learning Studio. Additionally, it supports R and Python functions that are user-defined. Table I gives a pricing comparison for Microsoft Azure.

TABLE I Price Breakdown for Microsoft Azure's Two-Tier Storage in the Central United States as of January 2018.

Cost	Current Price	Mean
Data Storage (per GB/Month)	0.0184	0.01
Write Request (per 10 K)	0.05	0.1
Read Request (per 10 K)	0.004	0.01
Data Retrieval (per GB)	Free	0.01
Data Write (per GB)	Free	Free

TABLE II The Top Algorithms' Cost-Efficiency and Quality Measures

Component	PaaS		IaaS		SaaS	
Original cost	€57.27		€129.12		€398.65	
Azure Autoscale	€27.42		€28.80		-	
Prediction algorithm	DRL		Neural Network		Decision Forest	
Predicted cost	€13.11		€16.29		€22.17	
Compared to original						
Savings (€)	€44.59		€121.74		€371.78	
Savings (%)	77.84%		89.37%		95.05%	
V as defined in the equation (11)	€0.07		€0.18		€0.59	
Compared to Azure Autoscale						
Savings (€)	{		{		-	
Savings (%)	€16.01		€14.11		-	
V as defined in the equation (11)	54.65%		48.22%		-	
	€0.03		€0.02		-	
	}		}		-	
Optimization factor	ACU	RAM	ACU	IOPS	DTU	Size
Root Mean Square Error	5.2716	0.1893	41.1788	17.0767	12.1190	4.4304
Mean Absolute Error	2.4648	0.0878	13.5869	7.7946	6.0438	1.8465
Relative Absolute Error	0.6542	0.4783	0.2312	0.9302	0.5525	0.2620
Root Relative Squared Error	0.7653	0.5976	0.4843	1.0457	0.6979	0.4783
R as defined in the equation (8)	0.00ACU	0.00 GB	0.00ACU	0.00 IOPS	0.0514DTU	0.00 GB

Using proactive consumption forecasting, anomaly detection, and effective provider-specific, automatic resource allocation, we discovered that none of the existing solutions consider the need to optimize different cloud resources (IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS) as well. We have created a system that can forecast and monitor in order to fulfill the aforementioned criteria. Using real-world use data, this work contributes by defining such a completely automated system and conducting simulations and testing of its behavior. You don't need to know how the system performs or have access to the original reservation schedules to use our solution. All sorts of resource characteristics are considered, like CPU, IOPS, RAM, and more; it's also compatible with many other kinds of cloud components, such as IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS. Because it is based on the cloud provider's pricing policy, the cost optimization method can handle usage spikes and price adjustments (such as periodic reductions) with ease.

CONCLUSION

Our system is able to predict future demand and modify the provided resources accordingly, resulting in a decrease in the cost of using cloud resources. Infrastructure as a service, platform as a service, application as a service, and any other cloud-based solution that uses scalable resources may be improved using our methodology. Although understanding the inner workings of the system under optimization is not necessary for resource allocation level optimization, our method will capture any performance gains made by the system and lead to future reductions in resource provisioning. Machine learning algorithms will identify complex, difficult-to-define, and time-varying consumption patterns; systems with these patterns will see the largest cost reductions as a result of our use of prediction methods. Though stateful communications make scaling resources easier, cloud providers also provide stateless communication scaling. This is because each call may be routed to the proper resource individually via stateless client-server communication. Many other kinds of cloud-based systems may function with our solution. These include web services for IoT hubs or Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, payment gateways for online transactions, e-commerce solutions, portals for online information, and social networks.

REFERENCES

- [1] Duan, S., Wang, D., Ren, J., Lyu, F., Zhang, Y., Wu, H., & Shen, X.((2023). Distributed Artificial Intelligence Empowered by End-Edge-Cloud Computing: A Survey. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 25, 591-624.
- [2] Murataj, S., & Doda, O. (2023). An approach in using Artificial Intelligence for traffic light optimization (fuzzy method). *Venturing into the Age of AI: Insights and Perspectives*.
- [3] Naen, M.F., Muhamad Adnan, M.H., Yazı, N.A., & Nee, C.K. (2021). Development of Attendance Monitoring System with Artificial Intelligence Optimization in Cloud. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence*.
- [4] Zhang, D. (2021). Storage optimization algorithm design of cloud computing edge node based on artificial intelligence technology. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 14, 1461-1471.
- [5] Wei, Y., Han, C., & Yu, Z. (2023). An environment safety monitoring system for agricultural production based on artificial intelligence, cloud computing and big data networks. *Journal of Cloud Computing*, 12, 1-17.
- [6] Ahmed, S., Yong, J., & Shrestha, A. (2023). The Integral Role of Intelligent IoT System, Cloud Computing, Artificial Intelligence, and 5G in the User-Level Self-Monitoring of COVID-19. *Electronics*.
- [7] Loseto, G., Scioscia, F., Ruta, M., Gramegna, F., Ieva, S., Fasciano, C., Bilenchi, I., Loconte, D., & Sciascio, E.D. (2023). A Cloud-Edge Artificial Intelligence Framework for Sensor Networks. *2023 9th International Workshop on Advances in Sensors and Interfaces (IWASI)*, 149-154.
- [8] Sadargari Viharika, E.A. (2023). Survey on Cloud Computing Integrated with Artificial Intelligence. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*.
- [9] Podder, I., Fischl, T., & Bub, U. (2023). Artificial Intelligence Applications for MEMS-Based Sensors and Manufacturing Process Optimization. *Telecom*.
- [10] Sangaiah, A.K., Javadpour, A., Ja'fari, F., Pinto, P., Zhang, W., & Balasubramanian, S. (2022). A hybrid heuristics artificial intelligence feature selection for intrusion detection classifiers in cloud of things. *Cluster Computing*, 26, 599-612.
- [11] Chaoraingern, J., Tipsuwanporn, V., & Numsomran, A. (2023). Artificial Intelligence for the Classification of Plastic Waste Utilizing TinyML on Low-Cost Embedded Systems. *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology*.
- [12] Rügsegger, M.B., Sommer, M., Rio, G.D., & Szehr, O. (2021). Deep Self-optimizing Artificial Intelligence for Tactical Analysis, Training and Optimization.

- [13] Vivekananda, G.N., Ali, A.R., Arun, S., Mishra, P., Sengar, R., & Krishnamoorthy, R. (2022). Cloud Based Effective Health Care Management System with Artificial Intelligence. 2022 IEEE 7th International conference for Convergence in Technology (I2CT), 1-6.
- [14] Ji, L. (2022). Application and Optimization of Artificial Intelligence Technology in Architectural Design. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*.
- [15] Ma, R., Kareem, S.W., Kalra, A., Doewes, R.I., Kumar, P., & Miah, S. (2022). Optimization of Electric Automation Control Model Based on Artificial Intelligence Algorithm. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*.
- [16] Yuan, X., Shi, C., & Wang, Z. (2022). The Optimization of Hospital Financial Management Based on Cloud Technology and Wireless Network Technology in the Context of Artificial Intelligence. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*.
- [17] Abro, J.H., Li, C., Shafiq, M., Vishnukumar, A., Mewada, S., Malpani, K., & Osei-Owusu, J. (2022). Artificial Intelligence Enabled Effective Fault Prediction Techniques in Cloud Computing Environment for Improving Resource Optimization. *Scientific Programming*.
- [18] Rao, P.D. (2023). Orchestrating Efficiency: AI-Driven Cloud Resource Optimization for Enhanced Performance and Cost Reduction. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*.
- [19] Sudha, D., & Chitnis, S. (2020). REDUNDANCY AWARE COST OPTIMIZATION IN WORKFLOW IN CLOUD COMPUTING ENVIRONMENT.
- [20] Hong, L., Deng, L., Li, D., & Wang, H.H. (2020). Artificial intelligence point-to-point signal communication network optimization based on ubiquitous clouds. *International Journal of Communication Systems*, 34.
- [21] Salem, R.K., Abdul Salam, M., Abdelkader, H.M., & Awad Mohamed, A. (2020). An Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm for Data Replication Optimization in Cloud Environments. *IEEE Access*, 8, 51841-51852.
- [22] Sharma, K., Doriya, R., Shastri, S.S., Aljrees, T., Singh, K.U., Pandey, S.K., Singh, T., Samriya, J.K., & Kumar, A. (2023). Development of Cloud Autonomous System for Enhancing the Performance of Robots' Path. *Electronics*.
- [23] Zhang, W., Zeadally, S., Li, W., Zhang, H., Hou, J., & Leung, V.C. (2023). Edge AI as a Service: Configurable Model Deployment and Delay-Energy Optimization With Result Quality Constraints. *IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing*, 11, 1954-1969.
- [24] Gómez-Carmona, O., Casado-Mansilla, D., López-de-Ipiña, D., & García-Zubía, J. (2022). Optimizing Computational Resources for Edge Intelligence Through Model Cascade Strategies. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 9, 7404-7417.
- [25] Li, J., Li, J., Liu, R., Tu, Y., Li, Y., Cheng, J., He, T., & Zhu, X. (2020). Autonomous discovery of optically active chiral inorganic perovskite nanocrystals through an intelligent cloud lab. *Nature Communications*, 11.

- [26] Pushpa, R., & Siddappa, M. (2021). An Optimal Way of VM Placement Strategy in Cloud Computing Platform Using ABCS Algorithm. *Int. J. Ambient Comput. Intell.*, 12, 16-38.
- [27] Strack, K.M., Davydycheva, S.N., Passalacqua, H., Smirnov, M.Y., & Xu, X. (2021). Using Cloud-Based Array Electromagnetics on the Path to Zero Carbon Footprint during the Energy Transition. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*.
- [28] Tiwari, A., Sharma, R.M., & Garg, R.B. (2020). Emerging Ontology Formulation of Optimized Internet of Things (IOT) Services with Cloud Computing.
- [29] Li, Y., Xu, X., Han, S., Wang, B., Dong, C., & Liu, B. (2023). Multipath Routing Scheme for AI Model Slices Transmission in Intelligent Networks. *2023 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, 1-6.
- [30] Xu, X., Li, H., Xu, W., Liu, Z., Yao, L., & Dai, F. (2022). Artificial intelligence for edge service optimization in Internet of Vehicles: A survey. *Tsinghua Science and Technology*.

Citation: Hemanth Swamy, Smart Spending: Harnessing AI to Optimize Cloud Cost Management, *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research and Development (IJAIRD)*, 2(2), 2024, pp. 40-55

Abstract Link: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJAIRD_02_02_003

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJAIRD/VOLUME_2_ISSUE_2/IJAIRD_02_02_003.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com